

Fagaridine Revisited[†]

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Fagaridine, a metabolite of *Fagara xanthoxyloides* and originally assigned structure 1b, was subsequently reassigned structure 1c. A recent synthesis of 1c by Nakanishi *et al.* points to the identity of 1c with fagaridine. The correlations leading to this final identity have been presented.

Fagaridine was isolated from *Fagara xanthoxyloides* by Torto and Mensah¹ in 1973. Ever since it has remained in prominence because of the antitumor properties associated with several benzophenanthridine alkaloids². Structure 1b (X = OH) was proposed for fagaridine on the basis of its conversion to chelerythrine (1a) and the position of the methoxyl signal in the ¹H NMR spectrum¹.

In 1988 we proposed that structure 1b for fagaridine is untenable on purely chemical grounds³. It was argued that in 1b the phenolic hydroxyl will be highly acidic due to the presence of the positive charge on the nitrogen atom and is likely to be deprotonated by the OH⁻ counterion. The so formed phenoxide 2 should be a resonance hybrid with a predominant contribution from the canonical form 3 due to charge neutralisation. Further, the extended conjugation in 3 should impart a deep colour whereas fagaridine was described as a yellow substance. To support this argument, we synthesised the model compound 1b (R₃ = R₄ = H) and studied its light absorption characteristics. The solid as such was purple in colour. Its solution in ethanol was deep violet which turned yellow on acidification. This change could be reversed by addition of ammonium hydroxide but on subsequent addition of sodium hydroxide the colour started to fade and ultimately the solution became colourless. These

changes were rationalised on the basis of interconversions 1 ⇌ 3 ⇌ 4. We felt this chemical evidence was strong enough to discard structure 1b in favour of 1c for fagaridine which, however, continued to be represented by the former. Very recently, Nakanishi and coworkers⁴ have synthesised a compound (NK 109) corresponding to the structure 1b and have shown that it gets converted to 3 at pK_a of 5.3. Further, these

workers have announced the synthesis of a compound with structure 1c. It has physical and chemical properties identical with those of fagaridine. Thus our original proposal has been fully vindicated after ten years. We can now offer an explanation for the erroneous conclusion of Torto and Mensah¹. Compared to the ¹H NMR model compounds considered by them, fagaridine has a free hydroxyl group: chelation of this OH with the adjoining methoxyl group can decrease the electron density on the oxygen atom and also restrict the orientation of the methyl group attached to it and thus cause a downfield shift of its ¹H NMR signal.

The fagaridine story has two important lessons. It brings into focus the importance of developing totally synthetic routes to target molecules because these can afford structural variants which sometimes may have better properties. The synthesis of compound NK 109 (1b, X⁻ = HSO₄⁻) is a telling example because its antitumor properties are far

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

superior to all the naturally occurring benzophenanthridine alkaloids. It is claimed to retain full activity against cisplatin and multi-drug resistant tumor cells and clinical studies have been carried out in Japan^{4,5}. The other implication of fagaridine work is that chemical sense still has relevance in organic chemistry research.

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